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Innovative Production of Samar-Based Suman with Assorted Fillings

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ABSTRACT

Title: Innovative Production of Samar-Based Suman with Assorted Fillings
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Gastronomists continuously modify and innovate the taste of suman by incorporating new twists with diverse ingredients to cater to the progress preferences of people wanting a fusion of suman with fruits and vegetables. This study aimed to innovate new procedures for creating Samar-based suman with assorted fillings (*Oryza sativa* var. *glutinosa*) and regulate the consumer's acceptability. Using the Hedonic 9-point scale, the acceptability of the produced suman (*oryza sativa* var. *glutinosa*) with Assorted Fillings in Terms of Appearance Mean= 7.56, Color Mean= 7.69, Aroma Mean= 7.59, Flavor Mean= 7.56, Taste Mean= 7.78 resulting in "Like Very Much." The physio-chemical properties of the assorted fillings in terms of Water Activity (A_w) resulted in $a_w = 0.916 + 0.002a_w$, with Total Soluble Solids (TSS) of $68.87 + 2.78^\circ\text{Brix}$ that indicates a relatively high concentration of soluble solids, implying a noticeable sweetness and potential impact on the shelf-life and microbial stability of the product. Combining the aromatic and sweet assorted fillings (mango, munggo, and carrots) with the sticky and rich suman creates a distinctive gastronomic experience that could cater to consumers' evolving tastes. This promising innovation combines two staple foods in traditional Filipino cuisine with modern nutritional considerations. Incorporating carrot fillings into suman combines tradition with modern nutritional awareness.

The modification of suman using mango, mung beans, and carrots as assorted fillings represents a convergence of traditional culinary practices with modern nutritional and entrepreneurial approaches. This innovation has implications for technology and livelihood education, providing a real-world context for teaching skills related to food technology, nutrition, entrepreneurship, and cultural sustainability.

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